

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 1

Acceptance of papers **January, 2026**

Acceptance of papers

Published monthly

Topics

economics, technology, social sciences

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THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

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ANALYSIS OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC INDICATORS OF INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL MANAGEMENT IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

Khosilov Shavkat Bekmurodovich

Acting Associate Professor of the University of Information Technologies and Management

Email: hosilov88@bk.ru

Abstract: Extensive research is being conducted in the world on the management of innovative potential in textile industry enterprises. Significant changes are being observed in the development of the textile industry. In this regard, "the center of textile production has moved from Europe and the USA to "third world" countries, in particular, Southeast, Central Asia, and South America." Textile enterprises in developed countries are increasing their competitiveness in the global market in a highly competitive environment by diversifying production, introducing innovations, and effectively managing personnel based on the effective use of modern management methods.

"Innovative potential" is a complex and multifaceted concept, the assessment of which requires the use of a number of indicators. In ensuring the assessment of the innovative potential of an enterprise, determining the optimal number of indicators and threshold values for each indicator, which will allow avoiding information gaps or the accumulation of excessive information, is an urgent problem.

Key words: textile, innovative potential, economic indicator, organizational indicator, autonomy coefficient, innovative project, reporting period.

Annotatsiya: Jahonda to'qimachilik sanoati korxonalarida innovatsion salohiyatni boshqarishda keng qamrovli tadqiqotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. To'qimachilik sanoati rivojlanishida sezilarli o'zgarishlar kuzatilmoqda. Bu borada to'qimachilik ishlab chiqarish markazi Yevropa va AQShdan uchinchi dunyo mamlakatlari, xususan, Janubi-Sharqiy Osiyo, Markaziy Osiyo va Janubiy Amerika davlatlariga ko'chdi. Rivojlangan davlatlar to'qimachilik korxonalarini ishlab chiqarishni diversifikatsiyalash, innovatsiyalarni joriy etish bilan bir qatorda zamonaviy menejment usullaridan samarali foydalanish asosida personalni samarali boshqargan holda kuchli raqobat sharoitida jahon bozoridagi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishga erishmoqdalar.

Innovatsion salohiyat — murakkab va ko'p qirrali tushuncha bo'lib, uni baholash bir qator ko'rsatkichlardan foydalanishni talab qiladi. Korxonada innovatsion salohiyatini baholashni ta'minlashda axborot yetishmovchiligiga yoki ortiqcha ma'lumotlar to'planishiga yo'l qo'ymaslikka imkon beruvchi ko'rsatkichlarning optimal sonini hamda har bir ko'rsatkich uchun chegaraviy qiymatlarni aniqlash dolzarb muammo hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: to'qimachilik, innovatsion salohiyat, iqtisodiy ko'rsatkich, tashkiliy ko'rsatkich, avtonomlik koeffitsiyenti, innovatsion loyiha, hisobot davri.

Аннотация: В мире ведутся масштабные исследования, посвященные управлению инновационным потенциалом предприятий текстильной промышленности. В развитии текстильной промышленности наблюдаются существенные изменения. В связи с этим «центр текстильного производства переместился из Европы и США в страны «третьего мира», в частности, Юго-Восточной, Центральной Азии и Южной Америки». Предприятия текстильной промышленности развитых стран повышают свою конкурентоспособность на мировом рынке в условиях жесткой конкуренции за счет диверсификации производства, внедрения инноваций, эффективного управления персоналом на основе эффективного использования современных методов менеджмента.

«Инновационный потенциал» – сложное и многогранное понятие, оценка которого требует использования ряда показателей. При оценке инновационного потенциала предприятия актуальной проблемой является определение оптимального количества показателей и пороговых значений для каждого показателя, что позволит избежать информационных пробелов или накопления избыточной информации.

Ключевые слова: Текстильная промышленность, инновационный потенциал, экономический показатель, организационный показатель, коэффициент автономии, инновационный проект, отчетный период.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan have paid special attention to increasing the competitiveness of textile industry enterprises, encouraging the production of products that meet market requirements and are export-oriented. The tasks set include developing indicators for the preliminary assessment of the situation in the real sector of the economy and introducing a system for their effective use; identifying and implementing factors and directions that will stimulate their development, taking into account the natural raw materials and labor resources of the regions and their relative advantages. In carrying out these tasks, it is advisable to further deepen scientific research on the optimal determination of the boundaries of the assessment of the effectiveness of the activities of managers of textile enterprises, and substantiating forecast indicators based on the proportionality of capital investments and management activities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The concept of innovation and its managerial interpretation has been widely discussed in economic and management literature, forming a solid theoretical foundation for analyzing innovative potential at the enterprise level. In this context, the Big Economic Dictionary edited by A.B. Borisov provides a comprehensive definition of innovation as an economic category, emphasizing its role in increasing production efficiency, competitiveness, and technological renewal. This source establishes the terminological basis necessary for studying innovation management mechanisms in industrial enterprises, including the textile sector.

The managerial aspects of innovation in industrial systems are examined in detail in Innovation Management in Industry by D.S. Kuznetsov, who considers innovation management as a systematic process integrating strategic planning, organizational coordination, and resource allocation. The author highlights that effective innovation management depends on the alignment of organizational structures with economic indicators, which is particularly relevant for textile enterprises characterized by high competition and rapid technological change.

A macroeconomic and long-term perspective on innovation development is presented in The Theory of Long-Term Techno-Economic Development by S.Yu. Glazyev. His theory of technological paradigms explains innovation as a cyclical process driven by structural shifts in the economy. This theoretical framework is essential for understanding how innovation potential at the enterprise level is influenced by broader technological and economic transformations, including those affecting the textile industry.

Strategic dimensions of management relevant to innovation processes are discussed in Management: Strategy and Tactics by Peter Doyle. The author emphasizes the importance of strategic flexibility, market orientation, and performance measurement in achieving sustainable competitive advantages. These principles are directly related to the organizational and economic indicators used to assess innovation potential management in enterprises.

The fundamentals of innovation management within the context of a transition economy are analyzed in Fundamentals of Innovation Management by M.B. Muminov. This work focuses on the formation, evaluation, and effective utilization of innovation potential in enterprises, highlighting the role of human capital, investment capacity, and institutional conditions. The author's approach is particularly applicable to textile enterprises in Uzbekistan, where innovation management remains a key factor in industrial modernization.

Sector-specific issues of innovation potential management are thoroughly examined in Improving Mechanisms for Managing Innovation Potential in Textile Industry Enterprises by Sh.B. Xosilov. This monograph proposes enhanced mechanisms for managing innovation potential in textile enterprises, taking into account industry-specific organizational structures, economic constraints, and technological capabilities. The study provides direct methodological support for analyzing organizational and economic indicators of innovation potential management in the textile industry.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that innovation potential management is a multidimensional process influenced by strategic, organizational, and economic factors. While classical economic and management theories provide a general conceptual framework, recent sector-oriented studies emphasize the necessity of adapting innovation management mechanisms to the specific characteristics of textile industry enterprises.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the important directions in increasing innovative potential, introducing innovations and creating the necessary conditions for its development is the correct formation of management. Taking this into account, we would like to turn to the process of innovation management and the system of indicators used to assess it.

It is proposed to use a number of indicator systems for analytical study of the process of innovation management in regions and assessment of its effectiveness. These indicators are divided into four groups.

Resources are needed to carry out any activity, including innovation, and assessing them using indicators that reflect the level of availability is the initial stage of analyzing innovation management.

Analysis and results

1) For employees employed at the ITTKI:

$$I_1 = \frac{L_{ITTKI}}{L_{um}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Where: L_{ITTKI} - the number of employees employed in the ITTKI sector during the reporting period; L_{um} - the total number of employees at the enterprise during the reporting period;

2) the share of employees with academic degrees and titles:

$$I_2 = \frac{L_{ilm.dar.un}}{L_{um}} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

In this: $L_{ilm.dar.un}$ - The number of employees with academic degrees and titles;

3) The level of education of senior and middle managers:

$$I_3 = \frac{R_{ol.mal.bosh}}{R_{um}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

In this: $R_{ol.mal.bosh}$ - the number of senior and middle managers with higher education in the reporting period; R_{um} - the total number of managers and specialists in the enterprise in the reporting period;

4) The desire and availability of opportunities for employees to improve their skills, retrain, and their share in the total number of employees is of great importance. The share of employees who underwent retraining and improved their skills in the reporting period is calculated according to the following formula:

$$I_4 = \frac{L_{mal.oshir}}{L_{um}} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

In this: $L_{mal.oshir}$ - The number of employees who underwent retraining and improved their skills during the reporting period;

5) The level of education and skills of employees is inextricably linked to the financing of their training and education at the enterprise. The indicators of expenses for training and education of employees are calculated based on the following formula:

$$I_5 = \frac{C_{o'q.va.tay.xar}}{C_{tex.inn.xar}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

In this: $C_{o'q.va.tay.xar}$ - Expenditures on training and education of employees in the reporting period; $C_{tex.inn.xar}$ - total expenditures on technological innovations in the reporting period.

The above indicators reflect the impact of human capital on the personnel potential of the enterprise. Let us consider the group of indicators that are proposed to be used in the financial assessment of the enterprise's readiness to implement innovative activities. This group of indicators shows whether there are sufficient or insufficient financial resources for the implementation of innovative projects.

6) The calculation of equity ratios, which includes the following ratios:

- retained earnings;
- specially allocated funds;
- other reserves;
- revenues and government subsidies that can be directed to the development and implementation of innovative projects at the enterprise.

Based on this, the need to analyze equity ratios is assumed when assessing the innovative activities of the enterprise.

The equity ratio is equal to:

$$I_6 = K_{xus.kap} \quad (6)$$

In this: $K_{xus.kap}$ - the enterprise's own capital in the reporting period.

7) Autonomy coefficient - characterizes the level of financial independence of the enterprise and expresses the stability of the financial position of the enterprise.

The coefficient of financial independence (autonomy) shows the extent to which the enterprise is financially independent. The lower the value of the coefficient, the greater the dependence of the organization's financing on debt sources, the lower the level of stability of its financial position. Average value: 0,4-0,6.

The autonomy coefficient is calculated based on the following formula:

$$I_7 = \frac{K_{xus.kap}}{K_{um.kap}} \quad (7)$$

In this: $K_{xus.kap}$ - private capital of the enterprise; $K_{um.kap}$ - total capital of the enterprise.

8) In our opinion, it is important to assess the total costs of technological innovations in relation to the total number of products shipped, works performed and services rendered during the reporting period. This indicator is determined based on the following formula:

$$I_8 = \frac{C_{tex.inn.xar}}{C_{mah.ish.xar}} * 100 \quad (8)$$

In this: $C_{mah.ish.xar}$ - Total costs incurred for products shipped, works performed and services rendered during the reporting period.

The next group of indicators allows you to assess the level of scientific and technical progress.

9) Each enterprise has a distinctive advantage, which characterizes the presence of promising areas, serves to determine whether it is provided with intellectual property and is determined as follows:

$$I_9 = \frac{V_{nom.akt}}{V_{ob.tash.akt}} \cdot 100 \quad (9)$$

In this: $V_{nom.akt}$ - value of intangible assets in the reporting period; $V_{ob.tash.akt}$ - the value of non-current assets in the reporting period.

10) The effective use of the innovative potential of the enterprise is assessed using indicators such as the number of scientific and technical developments, the share of innovations implemented in practice in their total volume. The innovative potential of the enterprise should ensure not only the development and creation of innovations, but also their implementation in practice. As a result, when assessing the innovative potential of the enterprise, we use the indicator of the degree of innovation, that is, the ratio of the total number of developed innovations to those implemented in practice:

$$I_{10} = \frac{C_{o'q.va.tay.xar}}{C_{tex.inn.xar}} \cdot 100$$

$$I_{10} = \frac{Q_{am.taq.inn}}{Q_{i.ch.inn}} \cdot 100 \quad (10)$$

In this: $Q_{am.taq.inn}$ - the number of innovations implemented in the reporting period; $Q_{i.ch.inn}$ - the total number of innovations developed in the reporting period.

11) The dependence of scientific and technical potential on the financial resources of the enterprise is expressed as the ratio of research and development costs to the total costs of technological innovations.

$$I_{11} = \frac{C_{tad.va.ish.xar}}{C_{tex.inn.xar}} \cdot 100 \quad (11)$$

In this: $C_{tad.va.ish.xar}$ - research and development expenses in the reporting period.

The next group of factors allows us to assess the state of the achieved production and technological level.

12) Fixed assets represent the production potential of each organization. The implementation of innovative projects usually requires a large number of machines, equipment, production sites and vehicles. The lack of fixed assets limits the implementation of the enterprise's innovative activities. Indicator I_{12} shows the level of provision of the enterprise with fixed assets:

$$I_{12} = AM \quad (12)$$

In this: AM - fixed assets of the enterprise in the reporting period.

13) When analyzing the innovative potential of the enterprise, it is necessary to assess its capabilities to master new types of production. For this purpose, it is proposed to use indicators of mastering new technologies:

$$I_{13} = \frac{AF_{\text{yangikir}}}{AF_{\text{yil.o'r.qiy}}} \cdot 100 \quad (13)$$

In this: AF_{yangikir} - the value of newly introduced fixed production assets during the reporting period; $AF_{\text{yil.o'r.qiy}}$ - the average annual value of fixed assets for the reporting period.

14) When assessing the level of innovation development of enterprises, the ability to produce innovative products is assessed by determining the coefficient of development of new products, which justifies the validity of the ban. This indicator is defined as the share of innovative products and services in the total volume of manufactured products, works and services:

$$I_{14} = \frac{IP}{TP} \cdot 100 \quad (14)$$

In this: IP - the volume of innovative products produced in the reporting period; TP - the total volume of products produced, work performed and services performed in the reporting period.

The provision of production - technological potential with financial resources is expressed by the following two indicators.

15) The share of expenses spent on the purchase of machinery and equipment.

$$I_{15} = \frac{C_{\text{mash.usk}}}{C_{\text{tex.inn.xar}}} \cdot 100 \quad (15)$$

In this: $C_{\text{mash.usk}}$ - expenditures on the purchase of machinery and equipment during the reporting period.

16) Share of expenditure on the purchase of technologies.

$$I_{16} = \frac{C_{\text{tex}}}{C_{\text{tex.inn.xar}}} \cdot 100 \quad (16)$$

In this: C_{tex} - expenses for the purchase of technologies in the reporting period.

The next group of indicators assesses the organizational and managerial potential of the enterprise.

17) The indicator presented below reflects several factors at once: the innovation management system, human capital, the socio-psychological environment of the enterprise, and the degree of compliance of the management system and organizational structures with the tasks of the innovation process. To determine the value of this indicator, it is necessary to evaluate a number of indicators in the questionnaire.

$$I_{17} = \frac{B_{\text{o'r.ball}^1}}{B_{\text{max.ball}^1}} \cdot 10 \quad (17)$$

In this: $B_{\text{o'r.ball}^1}$ - average score obtained on the questionnaire, $B_{\text{mak'ball}^1}$ - the maximum score that can be obtained on the questionnaire.

18) Determining the compliance of employees with the innovative goals of the enterprise based on the assessment of the system for stimulating their innovative (creative) activity is one of the main indicators of assessing innovative potential. To determine the value of this indicator, it is necessary to answer the questionnaire questions given in Appendix 3.

$$I_{18} = \frac{B_{\text{o'r.ball}^2}}{B_{\text{max.ball}^2}} \cdot 100 \quad (18)$$

In this: $B_{\text{o'r.ball}^2}$ - average score obtained on the questionnaire, $B_{\text{mak'ball}^2}$ - the maximum score that can be obtained according to the questionnaire.

19) The creative activity of the enterprise's employees and the level of readiness to implement innovative activities are also factors influencing the assessment of the enterprise's innovative potential. To measure it, a survey is conducted among the enterprise's employees.

Based on the survey results, the indicator of employees' readiness for innovation is calculated using the following formula:

$$I_{19} = \frac{B_{\text{o'r.ball}^3}}{B_{\text{max.ball}^3}} \cdot 100 \quad (19)$$

In this: $B_{\text{o'r.ball}^3}$ - average score obtained on the questionnaire, $B_{\text{mak.ball}^3}$ - the maximum score that can be obtained on the questionnaire.

20) The indicator below shows the innovative activity of an enterprise in relation to its size.

$$I_{20} = L_{\text{um}} \quad (20)$$

In this: L_{um} = the total number of employees of the enterprise in the reporting period.

21) In order to provide a general assessment of the innovative activity of the enterprise, the following indicator is used:

I_{21} - indicator of the overall innovative activity of the enterprise. This indicator is the integral value of the innovative potential of the enterprise, which is calculated according to the following formula:

$$I_{21} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{K}{n} \quad (21)$$

Where: K - is the value of the score coefficient, i - is the ordinal number of the coefficient, n - is the number of coefficients.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Thus, a structural assessment method for assessing the innovative potential of an enterprise has been developed, which has a number of advantages:

1. It is proposed to calculate the calculation of indicators within the framework of personnel, financial, scientific and technical, production, technological, organizational and managerial potential and the ability and readiness of the enterprise to innovate. Such a systematic approach to assessing the innovative potential allows not only to assess the factors that have a different indirect impact on the innovative potential of the enterprise, but also to identify the more important main reasons that have a decisive impact on the state of the system.

2. The proposed assessment method simplifies calculations by covering a relatively small number of indicators and, at the same time, ensures a sufficiently complete coverage of the elements of the innovative potential of the enterprise.

3. In this method, along with standard statistical indicators, generalized calculation data based on them is also used.

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Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 1

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